

IMPACT OF LOCAL TECTONICS ON THE DIAGENETIC ALTERATIONS OF PRECAMBRIAN UTCH KHATTAK FORMATION EXPOSED IN GADWALIAN SECTION, HAZARA RANGES, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Late Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation has been studied in detail at Gadwalian Section, Gandghar Range Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. Extensive fieldwork was conducted to mark and measure igneous intrusions in the form of dykes and to investigate diagenetic events associated with thermal effect of igneous intrusions on outcrop level. 47 representative rock samples were collected from affected zone of the 246-meter-thick carbonate sequence out of which 27 thin sections were prepared to delineate diagenetic alterations for the interpretation of effect of igneous intrusions on the host limestone of Utch Khattak Formation. Detail Petrographic study reveals that the studied formation is composed of Five main lithological units i.e., Argillaceous limestone which remained unaffected during this thermal effect, host limestone, dolomitic limestone which shows slight diagenetic effect, dolomite which is an indication of complete replacement and Marble. Marble was present at the periphery of igneous intrusions along the contact aureole zone followed by dolomite zone and then by dolomitic limestone. This study reveals that high energy is required for the diagenetic alteration of impure limestone i.e., Argillaceous limestone in our case. Petrographic study claims that the dolostone of Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation is of secondary nature for which the precursor limestone was deposited on intertidal to subtidal and inner shelf marine environment. Stoichiometric study explains that dolomite of the studied formation displays significant variation in crystal ordering. Diagenetic processes involved in reservoir modification were dissolution, dolomitization, micritization, compaction, neomorphism and cementation. Diagenetic events like dissolution, dolomitization and mechanical compaction show positive affect on the reservoir character of the target formation, while the chemical compaction, micritization, neomorphism and cementation plays a negative role by decreasing the reservoir potential of the carbonate successions of the Utch Khattak Formation. Field features, petrographic interpretation and geochemical investigations suggests that dolomitization model for Utch Khattak Formation is Burial Compaction Model and Hydrothermal Dolomitization.

INTRODUCTION

Carbonate rocks in fold-thrust belt settings play a key role in hydrocarbon and groundwater reservoir systems because deformation, fluid flow and diagenesis combine to control their porosity and permeability (Memon et al., 2023). Recent work in the Trans-Indus and Salt Ranges of Pakistan demonstrates that depositional architecture and early diagenetic processes exert a significant influence on later reservoir quality in carbonate-dominated sequences (Qureshi et al., 2023). The study area lies at Gadwalian section situated at Gandghar Range, Haripur district, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The Gandghar Range is located in the fold thrust belt at the southern margin of the Himalaya (Maluski and Matte, 1984) in the Hazara division round about 40 kilometers northwest of Islamabad (Yeats and Hussain, 1987). It forms a partial barrier between the Haripur and Peshawar basin (Yeats and Hussain, 1987). The Gandghar Range is bounded by the Haripur plain on the east and the Indus valley on the west. In the geological map of Pakistan (1964) the range is partly mapped as Precambrian and partly Silurian- Devonian succession and exposes a suite of metasedimentary rocks (R. A. Khan Tahirkheli, 1971). The Precambrian succession is well exposed in the northern Gandghar Range which includes Manki Formation, (thrust over Sheikhai Formation having faulted contact) Shahkot, Sheikhai and Utch Khattak formations. Among them the current research is focuses on the Utch Khattak Formation at Gadwalian section in northern Gandghar Range.

The Utch Khattak Formation was first named as Khattak Limestone and Baghdara Limestone applied by Tahirkheli (1970) and (1971) to lithostratigraphic unit in the Gandghar Range respectively and correlate them with unit in the Attock Cherat Ranges. Later the Utch Khattak Formation was modified from the name applied by Tahirkheli (1970) in the Attock Cherat Ranges currently used by the geological survey of Pakistan. This formation is composed of crystalline limestone with argillaceous streaks and lamination as described by Tahirkheli (1970). Predominantly this formation is comprising of rubbly and stromatolitic limestone with argillaceous laminations intruded by dolerite dykes. This formation also contains the clasts of Shahkot and Manki formations near Khairabad, at

Raja Hodi railway tunnel. It shows that the Utch Khattak Formation is younger than both Shahkot and Manki formations (Tahirkheli, 1970). Recent studies on carbonate units in northern Pakistan have emphasized how intrusive-related thermal and fluid processes drive diagenetic zoning and porosity evolution in fold-thrust belt settings (Rehman et al., 2023). Early geological studies (e.g., Wynne, 1879; Middlemiss, 1896; Cotter, 1934) provided the first stratigraphic descriptions of the Gandghar Range, which later served as a basis for modern lithostratigraphic classification.

Subsequent Geological Survey of Pakistan work (1950s-1970s) refined the stratigraphy and structure of the Gandghar Range, recognizing major lithological units and large-scale folds and thrusts (Calkins et al., 1975; Tahirkheli, 1970). Jamil et al. (2024) further demonstrated for Jurassic carbonates in the Trans-Indus Ranges that diagenetic overprinting linked to structural deformation strongly affects reservoir potential in similar tectonic-carbonate systems. Previously many researchers have studied and observed Utch Khattak Formation for sedimentological interpretations including Tahirkheli (1970); Yeats et al, 1987; Hylland et al, 1988; Hussain et al (1989). Also investigated that intraformational conglomerate within the formation contain clastic materials in Gandghar Range which is derived from the older Manki Slates and Shahkot Formation suggesting that the Utch Khattak Formation is younger than both mentioned formation (Tahirkheli 1970).

Yeats et al, 1987; and Hussain et al, (1987) has also done work on the formation and assigned the Precambrian age to the Utch Khattak Formation. Characterization of reservoir-scale porosity evolution in Paleozoic carbonate/tectonic systems in Pakistan has recently been advanced by Ahmad et al. (2023), but comparable detailed work focusing on the Utch Khattak Formation in the Gandghar Range remains scarce. Although several authors have mapped and described the lithology and regional stratigraphy of the Gandghar Range and the Utch Khattak Formation, previous work has emphasized regional mapping, lithostratigraphic correlation and general lithology, with limited detailed investigation of the

spatial distribution, timing and controls of diagenetic alteration related to igneous intrusions at the outcrop scale in the Gadwalian section. To address this gap, the present study documents the diagenetic zoning and paragenetic sequence around intrusion contact aureoles, characterizes dolomite stoichiometry and crystal ordering, and evaluates how intrusion-driven diagenesis and associated structural features impact the reservoir potential of the Utch Khattak Formation.

2. Regional and Local Geological Setting and Stratigraphy

The Gandghar Range lies immediately southeast of Tarbela Dam between the Haro and Indus Rivers, north of the Main Boundary Thrust (Figure. 1). The Gandghar Range is divided into northern and southern segments. Detailed mapping by the Geological Survey of Pakistan and subsequent structural analyses by Hylland (1990) established the basic lithostratigraphy and fault geometry of the Gandghar Range.

The Gandghar Range is positioned in Hill Ranges of northern Pakistan and consist of rocks that transitional between plutonic and high-grade metamorphic rocks to the north and unmetamorphosed foreland basin strata to the south (Hylland, 1990). The Gandghar Range in southern part is mainly consisting of a marine strata; series of possible Proterozoic age, consisting of a thick sequence of argillaceous sediments such as Manki Formation and this is overlain by shale and algal limestone such as Shahkot, Utch Khattak, and Sheikhai formations and these strata are intruded by mainly diabase dikes and sills and that can be correlate with the Panjal Volcanics (Hylland, 1990). The strata in Southern Gandghar Range occur in structural blocks juxtaposed along the Baghdarra fault where the hanging wall consists entirely of isoclinal-folded Manki Formation and the footwall consist of complete Manki - Sheikhai succession and which is deformed into tight southeast foreland (Hylland, 1990). The Gandghar Range comprises metamorphosed Precambrian strata that are

juxtaposed along major thrust and strike-slip faults, including the Baghdara, Panjal, and Khairabad faults, which collectively accommodate south-directed shortening within the Himalayan foreland fold-thrust belt (Hylland, 1990). The Utch Khattak Formation is exposed in the footwall of the Baghdara Fault within the Gandghar Range. The Manki and Hazara formations is said to be stratigraphically equivalent whereas in Kherimar Hills the Hazara Formation is unmetamorphosed while in Gandghar Range the Manki Formation is metamorphosed up to greenschist-lower epidote amphibolite grade (Hylland, 1990). The Gandghar Range sequence is matching to the sequence in the hanging wall of the Khairabad Fault in the Attock-Cherat Range while the Kherimar Hills sequence show resemblance in the footwall of Khairabad Fault; so according to this relationship it is said that the Panjal and the Khairabad faults are continuous and juxtapose laterally two chief structural blocks (Hylland, 1990).

Tahirkheli (1970, 1971) interpreted the Gandghar Range as a lateral continuation of the Attock-Cherat Range and correlated its Paleozoic sequence with lithologically similar units of southern Hazara; later work (Hussain, 1984; Yeats & Hussain, 1987; Hylland, 1990) revised the succession to show the Manki Formation as the oldest unit. A generalized stratigraphic column of the study area is shown in Figure 2.

Among these units, the entire paragraph explaining the Gandghar and Attock-Cherat ranges, consists mainly of shale, limestone, and argillite; the limestone is crystalline and commonly stromatolitic with argillaceous laminations (Tahirkheli, 1970; Kazmi & Jan, 1997). Intraformational conglomerates containing clasts of Manki and Shahkot formations indicate that it postdates those units. The formation is conformable with the overlying Sheikhai Formation and underlying Shahkot Formation (Yeats et al., 1987; Hylland et al., 1988) and is assigned a Late Precambrian age (Hussain et al., 1989). The crystalline limestone is thin-bedded to massive and typically grey to sooty-black in color.

Figure 1. (A) Showing study area in generalized tectonic map of northern Pakistan. (B) Map of the study area, showing outcrop locations (yellow color), major roads (heavy lines), and selected towns and villages (Hylland, 1990). (C) Showing the stratigraphic column of Attock-Cherat Range, Gandghar Range and others (Modified Hussain et al., 1989).

3. Materials and Methods

Multiple approaches integrating field, petrographic, and geochemical techniques were employed to investigate the diagenetic and compositional characteristics of the Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation in the Gandghar Range. Comprehensive fieldwork was carried out at the well exposed Gadwalian section of the Gandghar Range, where we collected 47 samples from Utch Khattak Formation and proper name and number was given to each sample. The Utch Khattak Formation are rich in dykes, and their width range from one foot to eight meters at different places. Each sample was collected from dykes at different position. There

were 15 main dykes in Utch Khattak Formation and 47 samples was collected from it at different position. Different other features like lithology, structures, textures and especially associated type of metamorphism and composition of magma were observed and noted. Standard geological field tools such as hammers and compasses were used for sampling and structural measurements.

Twenty-seven representative samples were selected for laboratory analysis and prepared as standard 30 μm thick thin sections at the Hydrocarbon Development Institute of Pakistan, Islamabad. Petrographic examination was conducted under a polarized light microscope (Olympus SZ61) at the Department of Earth Sciences, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad,

and microphotographs were obtained using an attached Olympus DP12 digital camera. Thin-section petrography focused on identifying mineralogy, textures, and diagenetic features, including cement type, compaction, neomorphism, and replacement.

To complement petrographic observations, geochemical and mineralogical analyses were performed as follows. Selected thin sections were stained with Alizarin Red-S and Potassium Ferricyanide solutions to differentiate calcite, dolomite, and ferroan phases (Bailey & Steven, 1960; Broch, 1961). Powdered samples were analyzed by X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) at the Hydrocarbon Development Institute of Pakistan to determine major and trace elemental compositions. Different microfacies of dolomites recognized on the basis of petrographic study were powdered and then prepared it for further analysis by mixing 20% Al_2O_3 and 80% of the rock powder (Guillet et al., 2007). Seven representative samples were further analyzed using X-ray Diffraction (XRD) with a PANalytical X'Pert PRO diffractometer (Cu-K α radiation, 45 kV, 40 mA, 0.2° 2θ min^{-1} scan rate) to characterize mineralogy, crystal ordering, and dolomite stoichiometry. The stoichiometry was calculated by using Lumsden's (1979) equation: $M = 333.3 \times d_{104} - 911.99$, and results expressed as mol% CaCO_3 . Crystal ordering of dolomite is obtained from the ratio of dolomite peak width at half max: intensity (FWHM).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Field Observations

Field investigations were carried out at the Gadwalian section of the Gandghar Range, northern sector of the Attock Cherat Ranges, District Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The study focused on the Utch Khattak Formation, a crystalline limestone dolomite succession intruded by numerous dolerite dykes, in order to assess the effects of intrusion-driven diagenesis on carbonate porosity and texture and to find the diagenetic alteration and the effect of igneous intrusions on the carbonate successions of the Utch Khattak Formation (Figure. 3AB). In total, about fifteen dolerite dykes were identified within the Utch Khattak Formation (Figure 3,4). The dykes range from approximately one foot to eight meters in width and produce marked thermal and structural overprinting on the host rocks. Lithological units observed include grey to black crystalline limestone, dolomitic limestone, dolomite, and locally developed marble adjacent to the intrusions. Common diagenetic and deformation features comprise stylolites, vugs, calcite and quartz veins, saddle dolomite, dissolution pits, and "butcher-chop" weathering (Figure. 3CG; 4H). The formation is well illustrated in the lithological column (Figure. 2), which summarizes its stratigraphic sequence, dyke compositions, and diagenetic events. Main task of our research topic is associated with Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation where we studied and collect samples from limestone and dolomite on the basis of outcrop features. A detailed lithological column of the Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation, showing dyke distribution, lithological variations, and associated diagenetic features, is presented in Figure 2. The field findings are shown below.

Figure 2. Detailed lithological column of the Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation exposed at Gadwalian Section, Gandghar Range Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Figure 3. Field photographs exhibiting prominent syndepositional and diagenetic features observed during detail outcrop investigations (A-B) Intrusion of intermediate igneous magma had caused contact metamorphism of the argillaceous microfacies of the investigate Utch Khattak Limestone evidently described the presence of marble horizon at the immediate vicinity of Igneous intrusion. Fluids evolved from solidified igneous intrusion had caused dolomitization in the precursor limestone adjacent to the marble horizon. (C) densely populated calcite veins within limestone beds of the target formation indicates intense diagenetic alterations. (D) syndepositional beds of the investigated formation is systematically altered by the process of dolomitization. (E) Identification of unaltered limestone beds in the field were identified by the presence of Honeycomb weathering within Utch Khattak Formation. (F) Field Photograph showing thermally metamorphosed zone (Marble Zone) along the contact aureole of igneous intrusion. (G) Field photograph showing different patches of dolomites within host limestone of the studied formation. Field evidences and petrographic study reveals that this diagenetic alteration has been accelerated by Igneous Intrusions within Utch Khattak Formation.

Figure 4. Detail field photographs indicate (A-B) intrabedded brecciated zone within Utch Khattak Formation representing intense diagenetic alterations in early stages of the limestone precipitation. (C) Highly fractured limestone beds within the studied formation. Geological address of the target area explains that this deformation has been induced by the Himalayan orogenic processes. (D-E) Igneous intrusions and its impact on the host limestone of the Utch Khattak Formation. (F-G) Contact aureole zone observed along the walls of dike within the investigated formation. (H) Field photograph showing butcher chop weathering which is used as a physical parameter for identification of dolomite bodies in the field.

4.2 Petrography

The dolomitization associated with Permian age dolerite dykes intruded in the Late Precambrian carbonates of the Utch Khattak Formation can be understood and recognized from the significant and key evidence obtained from the detailed study of various sedimentary features and diagenetic phases in conjunction with relative timing of various events. The observed microfacies correspond well with the lithological units documented in the field column (Figure. 2), where dolomitic and limestone intervals

are associated with multiple intrusive phases. Constraints on the three-dimensional association, timing and occurrence of various diagenetic phases that give rise to the existing, partially dolomitized, Late Precambrian carbonates in Gandghar Range are studied and examined by combining various techniques ranging in scale from outcrop to SEM. A detailed paragenetic sequence is constructed based on all findings and obtained results. Gadwalian Section is exposed along Ghazi-Panian main road in the vicinity

of Gadwalian Village, on the hanging wall of Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) and at the footwall of Baghdara Fault which act as a splay of Khairabad Fault System. Utch Khattak Formation is exposed in different sections of Attock Cherat Range. The thickness of the individual sections varies from 76 to 260m. Precursor limestone and different dolomite and calcite phases are sampled towards the top of sections. In all the sections east west or NE-SW trending bedding parallel and intrusion-controlled dolomite bodies are present in north-south direction across the sampled section.

4.2.1 Diagenetic Alterations in the Utch Khattak Formation

In Gadwalian Section, the Utch Khattak Formation is about 230 meters thick and well exposed. The studied formation has been intruded by large number of intermediate and basic composition dykes during Permian rifting in the vicinity of Peshawar Basin. In the studied area various rocks facies includes limestone, medium to coarse crystalline, planar dolomite (D-I), medium to coarse crystalline, planar to non-planar dolomite (D-II), fine to medium crystalline non-planar dolomite (D-III) and pores filling coarse crystalline saddle dolomite (SD). In addition to dolomite three calcite phases have also been recognized. These include twinned calcite (TC), white calcite (WC) and telogenetic calcite (TLC). Moreover dolomitization, brecciation, and stylolites have been observed seem and recognized (Figures. 5A-F; 6A-F; 7A-G).

In the study area the limestone of the Utch Khattak Formation in mainly medium to thick bedded, light grey to medium grey limestone. Limestone is light grey to yellowish color on weathered surface and off whitish grey to dark grey on fresh surface and is hard, compact and porcelaneous. Scars of burrowing was observed and seen in the precursor limestone. In some places Utch Khattak Formation possess stromatolites. Karstification is also observed in the precursor limestone (Figure. 6E-F; 5A-B). Stylolites are also quite common (Figure 6D). Limestone is partially dolomitized, and these dolomites are thickly bedded, show chop board weathering and forms scraps and weather to distinctive dark grey to blackish grey color. The limestone dolomite contact is sharp.

The dolomites are thick-bedded, exhibit butcher-chop weathering, and appear dark grey to blackish grey in outcrop (Figure. 6A-D). Different dolomite types were recognized and observed in the field. These include replacive matrix dolomite and partially dolomitized bed. Firstly, different dykes and its associated altered zones were measured. Samples were collected from these dolomite beds and dolomitic limestone and were examined under polarized microscope. Three main dolomitization phases are identified: matrix replacive dolomitization, selective dolomitization, and pervasive dolomitization. Detail field and petrographic study reveals that secondary dolomitization have completely and partially altered the precursor limestone beds of Utch Khattak Formation (Figure. 7C-E).

4.2.2 Replacive and Saddle Dolomite

Replacive dolomites occur as grey to dark-grey rocks showing sharp color contrast with adjacent off-white limestone. The contact between these limestone and dolostone is typically sharp. There are three types of matrix dolomite: (1) Type of dolomite (D-1) is grey colored and coarse crystalline dolomite, (2) Type-2 dolomite (D-2) is slightly dark grey color and is finely crystalline with sucrosic dolomite, and (3) White color, vein and Vugs filling saddle dolomite (SD) is also witness and in additional to matrix dolomite (Figures. 5A-F; 6A-E; 7A-D). The texture of replacive matrix dolomite (RMD) ranges from fine to coarse crystalline, displaying common intercrystalline porosity, generally meso- to macroporous in scale (20 μm -2 mm). The presence of various dolomite type in conjunction with overgrowth and crosscutting relationships indicates that dolomitization occurred in numerous phases (Figure. 6A-C; 7F-G).

4.2.3 Brecciation, Calcite Cement, and Stylolitization

Two types of breccia are observed in the Utch Khattak Formation. The dark grey color dolomite is brecciated which constitute dolomite breccia (DB). In DB the fragments are primarily of replacive matrix dolomite (RDB) (Figure. 7A-C). The ratio between volume of the breccia fragments and the pore spaces between fragments is about 3:1.

Stylolite have been observed and seen in the precursor limestone, in the dolomite and at the contact of

limestone and dolomite. In limestone as well as in dolomite the stylolites are parallel to the general trend of the beds and occasionally cutting dolomite veins (Figure. 7F-H). The stylolite extends laterally and

tends to continue for few meters. There is no specific pattern of specific between these stylolites, however in some set of stylolites a spacing of 4-5 cm is observed.

Figure 5. Photomicrographs exhibiting (A) finely to medium crystalline dolomite with recrystallized calcite as cavity and vein filling cement (B) Shows finely crystalline dolomites. Some of the fractures has been filled by calcite cement, (C) Fine to medium crystalline fractured dolomite but the fractures have been filled by blocky calcite cement and iron leachings. (D & E) cross polarized light photomicrograph demonstrates medium to coarsely crystalline, euhedral-subhedral dolomite crystals embedded in finely crystalline matrix, representing the early-stage diagenetic activities occurred at shallow depth due to meteoric effect, (F & G) Well developed (euhedral-anhedral) medium crystalline, dolomite crystals are embedded in finely crystalline dolomite matrix of the studied sample, (H and I) Matrix supported fine to medium crystalline dolomites.

Figure 6. Plain and cross light photomicrographs indicate (A-D) Medium-coarsely crystalline, euhedral-subhedral dolomites are embedded in finely crystalline dolomite matrix. It reflects matrix replacive dolomites. Some of the brown color micritic matrix is still unaltered. (E-F) indicates high influx of clastic input to the carbonate system. Quartz grains were embedded in fine-grained carbonate matrix; later, the carbonate matrix has been replaced by dolomite crystals. The dolomite crystals are very visible in the intergranular spaces. (G) Fine to coarsely crystalline dolomites of the studied formation, some dolomite grains has been altered by second phase of ferroan dolomitization. (H-I) Medium to coarsely crystalline replacive dolomites. Most of the grains are euhedral to subhedral in shape. Some of the euhedral dolomite grains shows zoning.

Figure 7. Plain and cross polarized photomicrographs of the representative samples represent (A) Medium to coarsely crystalline replacive dolomites. Most of the grains are euhedral to subhedral in shape. Some of the euhedral dolomite grains exhibit zoning. Fractures are filled with calcite cement and magnitude of stylolite is filled with iron leachings as well. (B-E) Finely crystalline Dolowackestone microfacies of the studied formation. The process of dolomitization seems to be matrix replacive dolomitization. (F-G) Medium-coarsely crystalline dolostone microfacies of the studied formation. Crystals exhibit Euhedral-anhedral texture as observed. The process of dolomitization seems to be matrix replacive dolomitization. (H-I) Demonstrates grain selective replacement dolomitization. Larger dolomite crystals are restricted to an inherited grain zone. Zone of larger dolomite crystals are embedded in finely crystalline dolomitized matrix.

4.3 Geochemistry

X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were employed to determine the bulk geochemical and mineralogical composition of representative dolostone samples from the Utch Khattak Formation. XRF quantifies major and minor elemental oxides, whereas XRD identifies mineral phases, crystal ordering, and dolomite stoichiometry (Lumsden, 1979; Reeder, 1990). We selected 7 samples for XRF analysis which was carried out at the Geosciences Laboratory, Islamabad.

4.3.1 X-Ray Florescence (XRF) Spectrometry Analysis

Qualitative X-Ray Florescence spectrometric analysis of 7 representative samples was carried out to define major and minor elements present in representative dolostone samples of the Utch Khattak Formation. All the major and minor elements were detected in oxides form present in table 1 and 2 and the corresponding XRF spectra are shown in Figure 8A-D. MgO, CaO, SiO₂, K₂O and Fe₂O₃ were detected

as major oxides while MnO, Na₂O, V₂O₅ and ZnO were identified as minor oxides. The values of CaO vary from 53.672 mol % to 91.2632 mol%.

Table 1. Shows Major oxides identified during qualitative and quantitative analysis of selected sample using X-Ray Florescence spectrometry.

Sample No	MgO mol%	Fe ₂ O ₃ mol%	SiO ₂ mol%	CaO mol%	K ₂ O mol%
SU-04	7.3285	8.8452	1.875	81.9513	0.0986
SU -09	0.9995	2.2648	13.2198	84.5731	0.4327
SU-16	3.4679	1.4573	1.4726	91.2632	0.4276
SU-21	1.8620	16.3828	3.5907	70.4416	0.1027
SU-30	3.9620	11.342	16.352	53.672	0.126
SU-36	5.9515	12.4826	17.8194	64.3142	0.127
SU-41	2.9173	6.6732	21.4321	68.2198	0.031

Table 2. Shows minor oxides identified during qualitative and quantitative analysis of selected sample using X-Ray Florescence spectrometry.

Sample No	MnO mol %	ZnO mol %	V ₂ O ₅ mol %	Na ₂ O mol %	Al ₂ O ₃ mol %
SU-04	0.0321	00	00	00	00
SU -09	00	00	00	4.7811	2.3272
SU-16	0.0271	00	00	2.339	00
SU-21	0.5563	0.0762	0.178	8.6717	00
SU-30	0.132	0.096	0.00	2.983	0.142
SU-36	00	00	0.0152	3.231	1.3954
SU-41	0.0824	0.0325	0.0326	5.5321	0.9635

Figure 8. (A-D) Showing XRF pattern of sample SU- 09, sample SU- 16, sample SU- 30, and sample SU- 36 respectively.

Figure 9. Graphical representation of geochemical compatibility of different major and minor oxides obtained from XRF analysis.

4.3.2 X-Ray diffraction (XRD) Spectrometry Analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed to identify mineral phases and determine the stoichiometry and ordering of dolomite crystals. XRD patterns of selected samples display distinct

reflections corresponding to dolomite, calcite, and minor quartz (Figure. 10). The main dolomite reflection (d_{104}) was used to calculate the molar % of CaCO_3 following Lumsden (1979):

{CaCO₃ mol % = 333.33 × d₁₀₄ - 911.99}

where d₁₀₄ is the position of the major peak in angstrom units. The standard error is ±0.15% on the mean composition with this procedure and the maximum difference for a given d₁₀₄% value, based on the "Lumsden line", is about 1.45% Ca the ordering of dolomite crystals was calculated from XRD data. The height ratio of the ordering peaks d₀₁₅ and d₁₁₀ gave a measurement of the degree of the ordering of the dolomite crystal. Greater the ratio, higher will be the degree of order (Main task of our research topic is associated, 1990).

XRD data were taken from X'pert High Score software, which is further, refined through Match! Software by using Fullproof program that has Rietveld

Refinement factor. As a result of these processes the experimental values in the form of a graph become matched with theoretical value and the measured d₁₀₄ values were used to calculate molar % CaCO₃ (Table 3). Graphs of the selected samples from each outcrop section have been given in detail along with given table 3. Each graph has its intensity value plotted on y-axis and 2-theta value on x-axis. The maximum peaks value d₁₀₄ gives the molar concentration by using Lumsden Equation. From XRD data the value of major and minor peaks was derived. These values enabled us to find the molar concentration of CaCO₃ and ordering for the dolomite. By using the Lumsden Equation and simple arithmetic calculation.

Figure 10. Showing XRD pattern of mineral phase of sample SU- 09, sample SU- 16, sample SU- 30, and sample SU- 36 respectively.

Table 3. Showing the molar% of CaCO₃ and ratios of peak intensities by simple arithmetic calculation and Lumsden equation.

Sample No	d ₁₀₄	I ₀₁₅	I ₁₁₀	I ₀₁₅ / I ₁₁₀	CaCO ₃ %
SU-04	2.8713	25.88	46.71	0.692	47.203
SU -09	2.7983	32.40	43.63	0.773	48.431
SU-16	2.8721	39.53	53.82	0.721	49.762
SU-21	2.8891	41.73	60.42	0.701	49.126
SU-30	2.8789	48.38	57.12	0.654	49.234
SU-36	2.8762	52.17	63.28	0.399	45.871
SU-41	2.8672	31.43	69.62	0.474	51.852

Figure 11. Showing the diagenetic stages for dolomite crystal. The data is taken from table 3 (After Lumsden, 1979).

5. Discussion and interpretation

Color changes, recrystallization, and increasing hardness toward dyke margins indicate contact metamorphism associated with the dolerite intrusions. Field relations suggest that dolerite

emplacement produced a contact-metamorphic aureole characterized by calcite-dolomite

recrystallization and localized formation of marble, accompanied by fracturing and veining (Figs. 4F-G). These textural and compositional modifications are

interpreted as evidence of intrusion-driven diagenesis that later influenced reservoir-scale porosity development in the Utch Khattak carbonates. Detailed petrographic studies were carried out on 27 selected thin sections representing the affected zones of Precambrian Utch Khattak Formation due to igneous intrusion in the Gadwalian Section of Gandghar Range. The studied dolomite zones at the periphery of Igneous Intrusions in Gandghar Range show different dolomite calcite phases besides host limestone. The immediate beds of precursor limestone in contact with dyke has been thermally metamorphosed by contact metamorphism. Then reaction zone were observed where fluids possess Mg reacted with host limestone and formed secondary dolomites. The third layer far away from intrusion zone possess dolomitic limestone and then we have unaltered host limestone of Utch Khattak Formation. Saddle dolomite occurs as vug- and vein-filling cement within coarse crystalline dolomite, often occluding pore spaces and fractures in dark grey color (D-1) dolomite (Figures. 5C-E; 6G-I) and has thus decreased and diminished porosity and permeability. Macroscopic pores are specifically filled by saddle dolomite cements (SDC). SDC borders the margins of larger pores in matrix dolomite. In addition to pores and vugs filling SDC, vein-filling SDC has also been observed and seen. The average thickness of majority of saddle dolomite veins in 3cm, though veins as thick as 10cm have also been observed. Separate dolomite packets are the main source from which majority of saddle dolomite veins radiate, diverge and spread. These veins tend to occur partially along stylolite's and do follow all existing fracture. SDC veins are crosscut by late-stage white calcite (WC), which indicates that saddle dolomite predates WC (Figure. 5F-G; 7D-E). The presence of saddle dolomite as cement and cavity filling is an indication of greater depth. Saddle dolomite forms at greater depth where geothermal gradient is high that's why saddle dolomite is considered to be indicator of high temperature regimes.

The ratio between volume of the breccia fragments and the pore spaces between fragments is about 3:1, indicates a high expansion, and according to (Billi, 2005) the existence of angular clasts of breccia and the lack of fault gouge specifies and shows that movements were very limited. Hence it is concluded

that hydro fracturing or revival and activation of the fracture by fluids is possibly results in DB. The second type consists of angular clasts of limestone and grey dolomite, reflecting brittle fragmentation and fluid infiltration proximal to dyke contacts. Dolomite phases are followed by calcitization phase. Two calcites have been observed, recognizes and seen which generally occurs in combination with dolomite bodies. These include telogenetic calcite (TLC) and white calcite (WC). WC occluded the vugs and pore spaces and has thus negative effects on reservoir properties. Both these calcite phases postdate dolomitization vein and thus postdates all diagenetic phases (Figures. 5A-C; 7D-E). The bedding parallel orientation of stylolite indicates bedding perpendicular direction of compaction. The amplitude of these stylolites generally up to 2cm, through stylolite with larger amplitudes has also been witnessed. Stylolite gives time limits for various diagenetic phases and features. These petrographic features collectively record a complex diagenetic history involving replacive dolomitization, selective and pervasive recrystallization, saddle-dolomite cementation, brecciation, and late calcite cementation (Figure. 5-7).

Wide variation in calcium oxide indicates effect of dolomitization fluid on different facies of precursor limestone. SiO_2 were detected as second major oxides contributing to the modification of Utch Khattak Formation. V_2O_5 contents vary from 0 to 0.1780 mol% which is lowest than other elements. ZnO varies from 0 to 0.0762 mol %. Petrographic study indicates that silica was deposited as clastic input. Silica value ranges from 1.4726 mol % to 21.4321 mol%. Fe_2O_3 is detected in all selected samples and its value ranges from 0.9995 mol % to 7.3285 mol %. Influence of magnesium has been recorded in most of sample in which value of magnesium ranging from 0.9995 mol % to 7.3285 mol %. MnO is also detected in few samples ranging from 0 mol% 0.5563 mol %. The overall compositional variation reflects progressive replacement of precursor limestone by dolomitizing fluids along intrusion-proximal zones (Figure. 9).

The calculated CaCO_3 mol % values vary across samples, indicating that the dolomites range from nearly stoichiometric to Ca-enriched compositions. Variations in the d_{015}/d_{110} ratio reflect differences in

crystal ordering, from well-ordered to partially ordered dolomite. These variations correspond to petrographic evidence of multiple dolomite phases and suggest progressive dolomitization under changing temperature and fluid composition associated with igneous intrusions. The data collectively indicate a transition from low-temperature replacive dolomite to more ordered, Ca-rich dolomite formed during later, higher-temperature diagenetic stages (Figure. 11).

On the basis of detail field investigation and petrographic study, subtidal to inner shelf marine environment is proposed as depositional environment for the precipitation of Utch Khattak Formation in late Precambrian age. Dolomites of the studied formation ranges from non-stoichiometric to nearly stoichiometric and less ordered finely to coarsely crystalline. The presence of saddle dolomite (which is a high temperature dolomite) as cavity filling and veins filling materials, indicates burial as well as thermally effected nature of the Utch Khattak Formation to a greater depth. Detailed field observations and petrographic data interpretation indicates that several diagenetic events are involved in the modification of Utch Khattak Formation. The studied formation is highly fractured, which is assumed to be deformed due to the active tectonic activities (Baghdara Fault and Khairabad Fault). Visual Petrographic interpretation explains that increase in porosity and permeability values are purely the product of dolomitization processes.

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